

THE ROLE AND THE OPERATION OF ALBANIAN LANGUAGE IN BALKANS

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Abstract:

Albanian language is the key of Proto-Indo-European languages. The aim of this paper is to research for the role and the operation of Albanian language in Balkans. The Albanian language is spoken by seven million people in the south-western of Balkans. Albanian is a language of the extensive Indo-European family and is thus related to a certain degree to almost all other languages of Europe. Albanian is officially spoken in the Republic of Albania and Kosova. Traditional Albanian settlements can be encountered sporadically elsewhere in Arbansi of Zadar (in Croatia); in some cities of Serbia; Macedonia; Montenegro and in the Bulgarian-Greek-Turkish border region. A few Albanian speakers are also to be found in the Ukraine (village in the regions Melitopol' and Odessa) and notably in villages in Bulgarian (in Mandrica). As a geographical and cultural entity, and as a nation, Albania has often been enigmatic. The first document in Albanian language is: Paulus Angelus, 1462 *"I baptize thee in the name of the Father and the Son and the Holy Spirit"*.

Keywords: Albanian language, Balkan, Indo-European family, grammar

Introduction

Albanian language has been noted above; the first millennium of Albanian history had little to do with the Albanian peoples themselves. As an ethnic group, the Albanians first emerged from the mists of history in the early years of the second millennium A.D. The name by which they became known, based on a root *alban- and its rhotacized variants *arban-, *albar- and *arbar-, first appears from the eleventh century onwards in Byzantine chronicles as Albanoi, Arbanitai and Arbanites, and from the fourteenth century onwards in Latin and other Western documents as Albanenses and Arbanenses.

It was the Swedish historian Johann Erich Thunmann (1746-1778), professor of rhetoric and philosophy at the University of Halle in Germany, who first postulated the Illyrian origin of the Albanians. In his German-language treatise *Über die Geschichte und Sprache der Albaner und der Wlachen* (On the History and Language of the Albanians and Vlachs, Leipzig 1774).

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Unfortunately, we know very little about language or languages spoken by the Illyrians because they left no texts or inscriptions. All we have are place names and personal names to go by. Scholars agree that Illyrian was Indo-European, but it is unclear whether we are dealing with one or several different Indo-European idioms. We also lack definitive proof that Illyrian, in any of its possible forms, is the ancestor of modern Albanian, as is widely assumed today.

The earliest contacts of the native population of Albania with the outside world were, as we have seen, with the Greeks who settled on the Adriatic coast at Epidamnos and Apollonia. Epidamnos (Gk. Ἐπίδαμνος) was settled in about 627 B.C. by Dorian colonists from Corinth and Corcyra (Corfu). In his work "Politics," the philosopher Aristotle (384-322 B.C.) tells us that there was much internal strife within the ruling oligarchy of the new settlement. When the Romans seized Epidamnos in 229 B.C., they changed the name to Dyrrhachium because the element -damnos in the Latin form of the name, Epidamnus, sounded inauspicious.

The word Dyrrhachium evolved into the Italian form Durazzo and later into the modern Albanian form Durrës. The Greek geographer Pausanias (ca. 115 - ca. 180 A.D.), however, tells us in his "Description of Greece" that the Roman town was not at quite the same site as the Greek one. Nonetheless, Dyrrhachium grew in the Roman period, in particular because it was the major Balkan point of departure of the Via Egnatia. The Latin poet Catullus (ca. 84 - ca. 54 B.C.) called the settlement Hadriae tabernam "the tavern of the Adriatic." In 48 B.C. the Roman military and political leader Pompey (Gnaeus Pompeius Magnus, 106-48 B.C.) deployed his forces here during the Roman civil war and vanquished Julius Caesar (100-44 B.C.) at the Battle of Dyrrhachium which was fought near Petra Alba (Shkëmbi i Kavajës), a few kilometres south of the town... The Albanian language, like all the other languages of the Indo-European family, has undergone great changes, thereby resulting in considerable developments and enrichment. These changes have affected the entire linguistic system of Albanian, including the lexicon, phonological and phonetic system, stress, morphological forms, word formation, sentence construction, etc. (K. Topalli, 2011). The tree of James Clackson books is very important for Albanian language. Albanian language is older than Greek and Latin languages. This theory evolved at the Cambridge University.

Source: James Clackson, *Indo-European Linguistics*, Cambridge University Press, 2007, p.44. This figure 1.4 (the 'Pennsylvania tree' taken from Ringe, Warnow and Taylor 2002)

Figure 1.2 *Schleicher's Indo-European family tree*

2. James Clackson, *Indo-European Linguistics*, Cambridge University Press, 2007, p.42

The grammatical system of Albanian was created as a result of complex combination of three linguistic elements:

1. Phonetics,
2. Morphology,
3. Syntax.

In terms of phonetics, it should be noted that various morphemes were involved in all the phenomena that are characteristic in the historical development of Albanian. Thus, for example, the majority of the inherited inflectional endings that contained full vowels underwent deletion or reduction. Hence, the majority of the contemporary endings, especially those with full vowels... The second factor that was quite productive in the creation of the grammatical system of Albanian is morphology.

- The noun, verbs etc., has the ending that is very important for example to creating plural nominal e.g: fushe + - fusha – fushe – fields.

Albanian language has five cases.

The definite and indefinite nouns (in singular and plural) in Albanian language has some different endings for masculine, *feminine* and *neuter* e.g. for masculine: -i, -it, -in, -it, -u, -un, -ut, for *feminine* -e, -a, -ja, -je, -s, -së, -në, or for *neuter* nouns with -i, -it etc. It is the full contrast between Albanian and English because in English the definite nouns for singular usually has article "the" but Albanian language usually has the endings (as in table A1, A2, A3) e.g.

The case Rasa	Indefinite –i pashqar singular – njëjës	Definite – e shqar singular - njëjës	Indefinite –i pashqar plural – shumës	Definite – e shqar plural – shumës
Nominative	libër - book	libri ⁱⁱ – the book	libra- boks	librat- the books
Genitive	i libri – of th book	i librit-of the book	i librave-of books	i librave-of the books
Dative	libri – the book	librit- the book	librave – books	librave –the books
Accusative	libër – book	librin- the book	libra- books	librat-the books
Ablative	libri – the book	librit- the book	librash- books	librave-the books ⁱⁱⁱ

Table A1: Masculine noun

The case Rasa	Indefinite –i pashqar singular – njëjës	Definite – e shqar singular njëjës	Indefinite –i pashqar plural – shumës	Definite – e shqar plural – shumës
Nominative	mik-friend	miku-the friend	miq-friends	miqtë-the friends
Genitive	i miku-of the friend	i mikut-of the friend	i miqve-of friends	i miqve-of the friends
Dative	miku-the friend	mikut-the friend	miqve- friends	miqve-the friends
Accusative	mik-friend	mikun- the friend	miqve-friends	miqtë-the friends
Ablative	miku – the friend	mikut –the friend	miqsh- friends	miqve-the friends ^{iv}

Table A2: Masculine noun

The case Rasa	Indefinite –i ashqar singular – njëjës	Definite – e shqar singular – njëjës	Indefinite – i pashqar plural – shumës	Definite – e shqar plural - shumës
Nominative	motër - sister	motra - the sister	motra – sisters	motrat - the sisters
Genitive	i motre - of sister	i motrës - of the sister	i motrave - of sisters	i motrave - of the sisters
Dative	motre – sister	motrës - the sister	motrave - sisters	motrave - the sisters
Accusative	motër – sister	motrën - the sister	motra – sisters	motrat - the sisters
Ablative	motre – sister	motrës - the sister	motrash – sisters	motrave - the sisters ^v

Table A3: Feminine noun

In the table A1 the first declension has some similarities, differences, contrasts between Albanian and English language or for Balkan languages. The noun /libër - book/ in the nominative case has the contrast because in Albanian it has the ending –i, for

ⁱⁱ Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, European Journal of English Language Teaching, <http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/295/742>

ⁱⁱⁱ Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST AND THE FUNCTION OF THE GENDER ALBANIAN TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE, European Journal of English Language Teaching Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/829/2366>

^{iv} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST AND THE FUNCTION OF THE GENDER ALBANIAN TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE, European Journal of English Language Teaching Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/829/2366>

^v Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST AND THE FUNCTION OF THE GENDER ALBANIAN TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE, European Journal of English Language Teaching Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/829/2366>

singular and /-a, -at/ for plural, than in English has the definite article /the^{vi}/ and in plural has ending /-s/.

The possessive case, in Albanian language can be realized with the article (*masculine, feminine and neuter*) **i** (m), **e** (f), **të** (n) and **së** (f) or with definite endings **-i, it, -in, -ve** (m), or **-u, -ut, -un** (m), but in **English** this case is used with the article **/the/** for definite nouns (m, f, n), so between two languages it is the contrast because it has two forms of possessive and usually used after the noun e.g. Mary's book, Time's house, students', worker's, children's, women's, This is Arta's jacket, This is my mother's jacket. This is the dog's food. If a plural noun does not end in /s/, add 's. women's, men's, children's etc. This phenomenon of grammar is the contrast between two languages.

Albanian language has a lot of endings for passive and active (demonstrative and adumbrative modality) verbs e.g.

		Mënyra dëftore Zgjedhimi vepror		Mënyra dëftore Zgjedhimi jovepror	
		Shkruaj			
E tashme	Unë	Koha e tashme shkruaj		Koha e tashme shkruhem	
	Ti	shkruan		shkruhesh	
	Ai/ajo	shkruan		shkruhet	
	Ne	shkruajmë		shkruhemi	
	Ju	shkruani		shkruheni	
Ata/ato	shkruajnë		shkruhen		
E shkruar	Unë	Koha e pakryer shkruaja		Koha e pakryer shkruhesha	
	Ti	shkruaje		shkruheshe	
	Ai/ajo	shkruante		shkruhej	
	Ne	shkruanim		shkruheshim	
	Ju	shkruanit		shkruheshit	
	Ata/ato	shkruanin		shkruheshin	
	Unë	E kryera e thjeshtë shkrova		E kryera e thjeshtë u shkrova	
	Ti	shkrove		u shkrove	
	Ai/ajo	shkroi		u shkrua	
	Ne	shkruam		u shkruam	
	Ju	shkruat		u shkruat	
	Ata/ato	shkruan		u shkruan	
Unë	E kryer kam shkruar		E kryer jam shkruar		
Ti	ke shkruar		je shkruar		
Ai/ajo	ka shkruar		është shkruar		
Ne	kemi shkruar		jemi shkruar		
Ju	keni shkruar		jeni shkruar		
Ata/ato	kanë shkruar		janë shkruar		
Unë	Më se e kryer kisha shkruar	E kryer e tejshkuar pata shkruar	Më se e kryer isha shkruar	E kryer e tejshkuar qeshë shkruar	
Ti	kishe shkruar	pate shkruar	ishe shkruar	qe shkruar	
Ai/ajo	kishte shkruar	pati shkruar	ishte shkruar		

^{vi} This definite article usually use before the noun.

	Ne Ju Ata/ato	kishim shkruar kishit shkruar kishin shkruar	patëm shkruar patët shkruar patën shkruar	ishim shkruar ishit shkruar ishin shkruar	qe shkruar qemë shkruar qetë shkruar qenë shkruar
E ardhme	Unë Ti Ai/ajo Ne Ju Ata/ato	E ardhme e së tashmes do të shkruaj do të shkruash do të shkruajë do të shkruajmë do të shkruani do të shkruanin		E ardhme e së tashmes do të shkruhem do të shkruhesh do të shkruhet do të shkruhemi do të shkruheni do të shkruhen	
	Unë Ti Ai/ajo Ne Ju Ata/ato	E ardhme e përparme e së tashmes do të kem shkruar do të kesh shkruar do të ketë shkruar do të kemi shkruar do të keni shkruar do të kenë shkruar		E ardhme e përparme e së tashmes do të jem shkruar do të jesh shkruar do të jetë shkruar do të jemi shkruar do të jeni shkruar do të jenë shkruar	
	Unë Ti Ai/ajo Ne Ju Ata/ato	E ardhme e së shkuarës do të shkruaja do të shkruaje do të shkruante do të shkruanim do të shkruanit do të shkruanin		E ardhme e së shkuarës do të shkruhesha do të shkruheshe do të shkruhej do të shkruheshim do të shkruheshit do të shkruheshin	
	Unë Ti Ai/ajo Ne Ju Ata/ato	E ardhme e përparme e së shkuarës do të kisha shkruar do të kishe shkruar do të kishte shkruar do të kishim shkruar do të kishit shkruar do të kishin shkruar		E ardhme e përparme e së shkuarës do të isha shkruar do të ishe shkruar do të ishte shkruar do të ishim shkruar do të ishit shkruar do të ishin shkruar	

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Koha		Mënyra habitore Admirative modality - Active Zgjedhimi veprorë	Mënyra habitore Zgjedhimi joveprorë Admirative modality - Pasive
E tashme	Unë	shkruakam	u shkruakam
	Ti	shkruake	u shkruake
	Ai/ajo	shkruaka	u shkruaka
	Ne	shkruakemi	u shkruakemi
	Ju	shkruakeni	u shkruakeni
	Ata/ato	shkruakan	u shkruakan
E shkuar	Unë	shkruakështa	u shkruakështa
	Ti	shkruakështe	u shkruakështe
	Ai/ajo	shkruakësh	u shkruakësh

Ne	shkruakëshim	u shkruakëshim
Ju	shkruakëshit	u shkruakëshit
Ata/ato	shkruakëshin	u shkruakëshin
Unë	E kryer paskam shkruar	E kryer qenkam shkruar
Ti	paske shkruar	qenke shkruar
Ai/ajo	paska shkruar	qenka shkruar
Ne	paskemi shkruar	qenkemi shkruar
Ju	paskeni shkruar	qenkeni shkruar
Ata/ato	paskan shkruar	qenkan shkruar
Unë	Më se e kryer paskështa shkruar	Më se e kryer qenkështa shkruar
Ti	paskështe shkruar	qenkështe shkruar
Ai/ajo	paskësh shkruar	qenkësh shkruar
Ne	paskëshim shkruar	qenkëshim shkruar
Ju	paskëshit shkruar	qenkëshit shkruar
Ata/ato	paskëshin shkruar	qenkëshit shkruar ^{vii}

Grammar is traditionally subdivided into two different but inter-related areas of study – morphology and syntax. Morphology is the study of how words are formed out of smaller units (called morphemes), and so addresses question such as “what are the components morphemes of a word like *atdhedashes - patriotic...?* *Syntax is the study of the way in which phrases and sentences are structured out of words, and so addresses question like “What’s the president doing? And what is the nature of the grammatical operation by which is component words are combined together to form the overall sentence structure?”*^{viii}

The contrast of Albanian language than Balkans languages are by some ways: The kind and the function of endings (noun and verb), the kind and the function of the words in the sentence.

The syntactic structure of Albanian language is different than the one of all the languages in Balkans. By the endings of the verbs (predicate) it is possible to find the subject^{ix}. The noun is the head of the sentence, because it is subject, direct and indirect object but with the endings of the verb the noun can missig e.g.

Punoj në shtëpi – I work at home.

Studenti kishte takuar **profesorin** para **provimit** - (Kishte takuar **profesorin** para **provimit**)

S P IO DO

Customarily, linguistic description on the syntactic level is formulated in terms of constituent analysis. We now can ask what form of grammar is presupposed by description of this sort. We find that the new form of grammatical is essentially more powerful than the finite state model rejected above, and that the associated concept of “linguistic level” is different in fundamental respects. “*Noun phrases are any and all structures headed by a noun, or by a pronoun, or any other word or structure that stands in for a*

^{vii} Shkelqim Millaku, *Tekst ushtrimesh për lakimin e emrave dhe zgjedhimin e foljeve*, Prishtinë, 2017, f.66

^{viii} Andrew Radford. (2004). **English Syntax**. Cambridge, p. 1

^{ix} Shkelqim Millaku, *The subject*.

noun. Thus even an entire clause may function as a noun phrase". Some further evidence that categories are complex entities comes from the fact that phrase categories go together with, or are "projection" of, specific word level categories. This was first highlighted in Harris (1951) and was taken up in Chomsky (1970)², Jackendoff (1977) or Muysken 1985 etc. As a simple example of the new form for grammar associated with constituent analysis, consider the following. (i) Sentence NP +VP (ii) NP – T+N (iii)VP- Verb + NP (iv) T – the (v) N – man, ball, etc. (vi) Verb – hit, took^x, etc .

Conclusion

Albanian is an Indo-European language and, thus, its grammatical system has its genesis in the ancient language of Proto-Indo-European^{xi}. The first document in Albanian language is: Paulus Angelus (Pal Engjulli), 1462 *"I baptize thee in the name of the Father and the Son and the Holy Spirit"*.

The rules for the placement of the words are possible to change from any language to other languages. The grammatical system of Albanian was created as a result of complex combination of three linguistic elements: Phonetics, Morphology and Syntax.

The role and the function of Albanian language in Balkan is different with all the languages that are spoken in Balkan. Albanian language is native. The status of Albanian language in Balkans is not in the good situation. In some countries isn't office language like in Serbia and Macedonia etc.

Albanian language is the key of Proto-Indo-European languages.

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^x Shkelqim Millaku, The noun phrase,

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^{xi} Kolec Topalli, Gramatike historike e gjuhës shqipe, Tiranë, 2011, f. 1398

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